

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following guidelines and style

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg ha.
- When using abbreviations other than for units of measure, spell out the full name the first time of reference, with abbreviations in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were ... or Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotypes of BPH in ...
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage. Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the *IRRN* should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source of genetic resistance to rice pests).
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common — not trade — names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible, equipment.
- Do not include references in *IRRN* contributions.
- Pest surveys should be quantified with data (% infection, degree of severity, etc.).

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Identification of long-duration semidwarf rice cultivars for low-lying situations in different agroclimatic zones of West Bengal

P. Mukherjee and A. R. Debnath, Rice Research Station (RRS), Chinsurah, West Bengal, India

A multilocation investigation was conducted during the 1979 wet season to identify suitable rice cultivars for low-lands (20-50 cm water level) in specific agroclimatic zones in West Bengal. The entries were promising rice cultivars of diverse genetical constitution from coordinated trials, and mutant and hybrid derivatives developed at RRS, Chinsurah; the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack; other institutions of India and IRRI.

Sixteen promising long-duration (140 days or longer in the wet season) semidwarf rice cultivars were fitted in a

randomized block design with 3 replications. Plot size (net) was 4.6 × 2.7 m, with a spacing of 20 × 15 cm. Fertilizer was applied at a rate of 80 N:40 P₂O₅:40 K₂O kg/ha.

The table shows that at Chinsurah, grain yields ranged between 5 t/ha for CR1011 and 2.4 t/ha for CNM539. CR1006 (4.8 t/ha) and Pankaj (check) (4.7 t/ha) ranked 2d and 3d.

At Bankura, the grain yield was poor because of drought. Nevertheless, IR34 and IR4219-35-3-3 yielded nearly 3 t/ha and CR1002 and IET5638 yielded 2 t/ha. CO 40 was completely damaged.

The trial at Krishnanagar also suffered because of drought. Only IR4219-35-3-3 yielded 2.6 t/ha, and Pankaj (check) yielded only 1.9 t/ha.

On the basis of average grain yields at three sites, the cultivars IR4219-35-3-3, Pankaj, IR34, CR1002, and CR1006 are suitable for low-lying areas in different zones of West Bengal. ■

Mean yield of long-duration semidwarf rice cultivars in low-lying areas during 1979 wet season at 3 sites in West Bengal, India.

Cultivar	Growth duration (days)	Grain yield (t/ha)			
		Chinsurah	Rankura	Krishnanagar	Varietal mean
CR1002	142	4.4	2.0	1.4	2.6**
CR 1006	160	4.8*	0.8	1.7	2.6**
CR 1009	152	4.3	1.2	1.3	2.3
CR1010	156	4.5*	0.9	1.3	2.2
CR1011	151	5.0*	0.7	1.3	2.3
IET5638	145	4.4	2.0	0	2.1
IET5656	155	4.2	1.9	0.7	2.3
CO 38	143	3.6	1.9	0.8	2.1
CO 40	170	4.0	0	0.5	1.5
CN 195	143	3.7	1.4	0.6	1.9
CN643	150	3.7	1.2	0.8	1.9
CN644	154	3.5	1.3	0.5	1.8
CNM539	145	2.4	1.1	0.8	1.4
IR34	140	3.6	2.9*	1.6	2.7**
IR4219-35-3-3	150	4.0	2.9*	2.6*	3.2**
Pankaj (check)	145	4.7*	1.8	1.9	2.8**
L.S.D. (0.05)		0.5	0.6	0.4	

*Indicates at par. **Indicates recommended.

Delay in flowering of some lines during rapid generation advance

S. K. Bardhan Roy, B. S. Vergara, and G. Pateña, Plant Physiology Department, International Rice Research Institute

In the rapid generation advance (RGA) method the plants are subjected to short days and high temperature so they can be harvested 60-90 days after sowing. But we have noted that the flowering of